

Determinants of Unwanted Pregnancy in Indonesia in 2022

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ABSTRACT: Unwanted pregnancy in teenagers is the impact of deviant sexual behavior. Adolescents with Unwanted pregnancy are faced with various problems, especially health problems for mothers and babies, and socio-economic problems. This research aims to examine the determinants of untimely pregnancy in adolescents in North Konawe Regency. The research design uses a Cross Sectional Study conducted in September 2022-February 2023 in three randomly selected sub-districts of North Konawe Regency. A total of 80 teenage girls aged 14-19 years who experienced untimely pregnancy were sampled. The research uses a structured questionnaire technique guided by researchers which has been previously tested and analyzed using the Fisher Exact test. The results of the bivariate analysis showed that the variables were Knowledge ($p=0.568>0.05$), Attitude ($p=0.002<0.05$), Action ($p=0.74>0.05$), Permissive Parenting Pattern ($p=0.109>0.05$), Peer Pressure Peers ($p=0.592>0.05$), Use of Technology ($p=0.034<0.05$) and Religiosity ($p=0.001<0.05$). The results of this research show that there is a relationship between Attitude, Use of Technology and Religiosity, and there is no relationship between Knowledge, Action, Permissive Parenting Patterns and Peer Pressure with Unwanted Pregnancy in teenagers in the North Konawe Regency Area. Thus, the Reproductive Health Education program for Adolescents in formal education involves education stakeholders including the School Committee which is a reference material and a program to reduce the number of unwanted pregnancy in adolescents in the North Konawe Regency area.

KEYWORDS: Unwanted Pregnancy; knowledge; attitude; action; permissive parenting; use of technology; religiosity.

INTRODUCTION

Adolescence is a transition period towards adulthood. Teenage life is a life that determines a person's future and what is most important is because the state hopes that teenagers as the young generation will become the successors of the nation's future. On the other hand, adolescence is also considered a period of change, namely the level of changes in attitudes and behavior accompanied by physical changes. The adolescent phase is a period full of turmoil and full of dynamic events that mark the characteristics of adolescence. Adolescence is also considered a period of human transition because many changes occur, both physical and psychological [1,2]. During the transition period, teenagers experience various kinds of changes between one life and another and they have different abilities in understanding, appreciating and digesting the knowledge and experiences they receive. Therefore, adolescence is an important stage in human life that requires attention, guidance and empathy from parents and the surrounding community [3].

Unwanted teenage pregnancies are estimated at 50% of the 21 million pregnancies that occur each year and 55% of these teenage pregnancies end in abortion. [4]. Save the Children estimates that the economic impact of the COVID19 crisis caused 1 million more teenage pregnancies in 2020[1,5]. In Southeast Asia, the average birth rate to teenage mothers is 48 births per 1,000 women aged 15-19 years, higher than the average in South Asia, namely 35 births, and close to the global average, namely 50 births. The highest rates of teenage pregnancy globally were recorded in Laos (94), Cambodia (57), Thailand (50), Indonesia (48), and the Philippines (47)[6].

Several studies have found that unwanted pregnancy and risky adolescent sexual behavior are the reasons for the increasing number of early marriages in Indonesia. Early marriage is a marriage carried out by teenagers aged < 20 years, amounting to 53 per 1000 teenagers. This figure increased to 24,000 during the Covid-19 pandemic [7]. The Directorate General of Religious Courts noted that there were 64,211 marriage dispensations granted in 2020, this figure increased approximately threefold or 177.7% from 2019 which was 23 per 100,000 marriage dispensations [8– 11].

The impact of early marriage has various risks due to the unpreparedness of young women to accept pregnancy, giving birth and caring for children, including low awareness of Antenatal Care (ANC) which contributes to high maternal, infant and under-five

mortality rates. The MMR in Indonesia is reported to be 305 per 100,000 live births and the IMR is 11.7 per 1000 live births in 2019 (Karaçam *et al.*, 2021; Kemenkes RI, 2020). Teenage pregnancy increases the risk of stillbirth, neonatal death, LBW and prematurity by 50%. Babies born prematurely have a big chance of stunting [15]. This is proven by data that stunting in Indonesia has reached 24.4%. This means that 1 in 4 children in Indonesia experience stunting [14].

Teenage pregnancy also increases the risk of unsafe abortion. Bain *et al.*'s (2020) study found that 87.0% of 15 teenagers had experience of abortion performed unsafely. The case of abortion in teenage pregnancies is also supported by studies Atuhaire (2019) which states that in developing countries 98% of unsafe abortions are recorded every year and 41% of abortion perpetrators are teenagers under the age of 20. Abortion is a shortcut chosen by teenagers to escape the problem of unwanted pregnancy [17]. Based on the characteristics of abortion perpetrators, it was found that 40.3% of teenagers had had sex for the first time at the age of 13-15 years [18].

Another impact of teenage pregnancy is on socio-economic life. Socio-economic maturity in marriage is very necessary, because it is a support for the wheels of the family as a result of marriage (Franjic, 2018; Syalis, E. R., & Nurwati, N. N, 2020). The percentage of population living below the 2019-2020 National Poverty Line in Indonesia shows that a poverty rate of 12.64% is seen in the age group <18 years (BPS Indonesia, 2022). Research by [20] shows that 44% of early marriage perpetrators experience domestic violence, which is closely related to cases of economic neglect.

Unwanted Pregnancy in teenagers is one of the results of risky premarital sexual behavior and as a result of teenage curiosity (Prihayati *et al.*, 2020; Shrestha, 2019). Risky adolescent sexual behavior can be caused by 2 factors, namely; internal factors and external factors. Based on several studies, it was found that factors can influence the incidence of untimely pregnancy in adolescents, namely knowledge, attitudes and actions [24] ([24]; Ayele *et al.*, 2018; Jannah, 2018; Fitriani *et al.*, 2019; Sunardi *et al.*, 2020) and external factors are permissive parenting patterns, peer pressure, use of technology and religiosity [25].

Knowledge is one of the predictors of adverse events in adolescents. Ayele's research (2018) shows that 52.9% of respondents who experienced Unwanted Pregnancy had poor knowledge about the occurrence of conception. Likewise research conducted by Fitriani (2019) shows that teenagers who have low knowledge about sexuality have a greater chance of engaging in deviant premarital sexual behavior compared to teenagers who have good knowledge [25].

Attitude is readiness or willingness to take action. For example, teenagers' sexual attitudes will be related to untimely pregnancy as a result of deviant sexual behavior [27]. Adolescents who have a negative attitude towards having sexual relations before marriage have a 9.91 chance of committing risky sexual acts [28]. Research conducted by Jannah (2018) with 103 respondents with Unwanted Pregnancy having negative sexual attitudes. A series of actions is a direct direction from an attitude, if a negative attitude supports it, it will also form a negative action [28]. The 2017 Indonesian Demographic and Health Survey highlights that adolescent girls and boys who have/are currently dating have risky behavior. This is proven by the fact that 28% of female teenagers stated that they had been exposed to several forms of risky sexual behavior, such as hugging, kissing, touching and touching sexual organs [30].

Another determinant that significantly describes the impact of dating is support from parents. Adolescents who receive support from their parents in dating are 1,396 times more likely to engage in premarital sexual behavior compared to those who do not receive support [26]. The permissive attitude of parents plays a very important role in promiscuity which is a determining factor for untimely pregnancy in adolescents, namely 2,176 times [31]. Research conducted by Jannah & Cahyono (2021) also shows that there is a significant relationship between parenting styles that give freedom to their children and pre-marital sexual behavior, 94.4% of respondents who have permissive parenting styles in the very high category have pre-marital sexual behavior.

Another factor, namely peer pressure, is another determinant of risky sexual behavior that can have an impact on adolescent pregnancy loss [25]. Qualitative study conducted Faudzi *et al* (2022) found that peer pressure also has a risky influence. Most teenagers who are friends with those who behave deviantly, make these teenagers influenced and involved in risky sexual behavior. Data proves that quite a few of them end up with untimely pregnancy. Study results Damtie *et al* (2022) also shows there is a relationship between peer pressure and premarital sexual practices. The results showed that young individuals who experienced peer pressure were three times more likely to engage in premarital sex [34].

Another trigger that has a negative impact on the determinants of risky sexual behavior in adolescents is the use of technology. Study [35] shows that exposure to pornography increases the risk 8 times of committing deviant sexual behavior. In line with the research conducted Novita et al (2018) also shows a significant relationship between the frequency of exposure to pornography and adolescent sexual behavior which leads to untimely pregnancy.

Religiosity is also one of the triggering factors that makes teenagers engage in risky sexual behavior which leads to untimely pregnancy (Sari & Indriani, 2021, Panting et al., 2019). Teenagers who have low religiosity and are dating, they will be more at risk. It was found that teenagers with low religiosity are 3 times more likely to be at risk of deviant sexual behavior compared to teenagers with high religiosity [37].

An initial survey of health services at the North Konawe District Health Service found that 158 teenagers experienced pregnancy. They are among mothers at high risk, especially in the 2020-2022 Covid-19 pandemic era. So teenage pregnancy in North Konawe Regency is a problem for the Health Service and is also a concern for the North Konawe Regency BKKBN. On the other hand, stunting data in North Konawe Regency is also a health problem with a history of teenage mothers. This case involves other agencies that also focus on stunting programs, including the Education Agency, the Women's Empowerment and Child Protection agency and others.

Based on the background above, the author will present the results of a study that has been carried out with the title "Determinants of Unwanted Pregnancy in Adolescents in the North Konawe Regency Area in 2022".

RESEARCH METHODS

This research is a quantitative study using an observational analytical design with a cross sectional approach, to determine the results of the determinants of untimely pregnancy in adolescents in the North Konawe Regency area. This research was carried out in 3 randomly selected sub-districts, namely Asera District, Andowia District and Molawe District. The population is female adolescents aged 10-19 years with unwanted unplanned pregnancy (due to coercion) and occurring outside of marriage for the 2020-2022 period. The sample consisted of 80 people using the Total Sampling method and the research instrument was a structured questionnaire which had been tested for its level of validity and reliability. This illustrates that this study instrument was developed by the researchers themselves. Primary data collection was carried out using a structured and self-guided questionnaire. Meanwhile, secondary data was obtained from various sources, for example health center reports, previous research journals and other sources. Data analysis uses univariate, bivariate and multivariate analysis using the Logistic Regression Test. Statistical analysis uses Fisher's Exact Test and the results of the analysis are presented in quantitative descriptive terms and the dominant and most significant determinants of Unwanted Pregnancy are obtained.

RESULTS

The Relationship between Knowledge and Unwanted Pregnancy in Adolescents in the North Konawe Regency Area.

Table 1. Relationship between Knowledge and Unwanted Pregnancy among teenagers in the North Konawe Regency

No	Knowledge	Unwanted Pregnancy				Total		P Value
		Yes		Not		n	%	
		n	%	n	%			
1	Lacking	55	68,8	4	5	59	73,8	0,568
2	Good	21	26,2	0	0	21	26,2	
Total		76	95,0	4	5,0	80	100	

Table 1 shows that of the 59 respondents who had less knowledge, there were 55 respondents (68.8%) who experienced an unlucky event and only 4 respondents (5%) did not experience an unlucky pregnancy. Meanwhile, of the 21 respondents who had good

knowledge, all had experienced untimely pregnancy, there was not a single respondent who had not experienced unfavorable pregnancy. The results of statistical tests using Fisher's Exact Test obtained a value (p value = $0.568 > 0.05$), so H_a was rejected and H_o was accepted. This means that there is no relationship between teenagers' knowledge and Unwanted Pregnancy in the North Konawe Regency area in 2022. From the analysis above, it shows 4 respondents who had less knowledge but did not experience Unwanted Pregnancy.

The Relationship between Attitude and Unwanted Pregnancy in Adolescents in the North Konawe Regency Area.

Table 2. Relationship between attitudes and Unwanted Pregnancy in adolescents In the North Konawe Regency

No	Attitude	Unwanted Pregnancy				Amount		P Value
		Yes		Not		n	%	
		n	%	n	%			
1	Negative	72	90	1	1.25	73	91.25	0,002
2	Positive	4	5	3	3.75	7	8.75	
Total		76	95.0	4	5.0	80	100	

Table 2 shows that of the 73 respondents who had a negative attitude, there were 72 respondents (90.0%) who experienced an unlucky event and only 1 respondent (1.25%) did not experience an unlucky pregnancy. Meanwhile, of the 7 respondents who had a positive attitude, there were 4 respondents (5.0%) who experienced an unlucky pregnancy and 3 respondents (3.75%) who did not experience an unlucky pregnancy. The results of the statistical analysis test using Fisher's Exact Test obtained a value (p value = $0.002 < 0.05$), so H_a was accepted and H_o was rejected. This means that there is a relationship between adolescent attitudes and Unwanted Pregnancy among teenagers in the North Konawe Regency area in 2022. From these data it can be said that the majority of respondents with negative attitudes experienced Unwanted Pregnancy.

The Relationship between Actions and Unwanted Pregnancies in Adolescents in the North Konawe Regency Area.

Table 3. Correlation of Actions with Unwanted Pregnancy in Adolescents In the North Konawe Regency area

No	Action	Unwanted Pregnancy				amount		P Value
		Ya		Tidak		n	%	
		n	%	n	%			
1	Negative	68	85,0	2	2.5	70	87.5	0,074
2	Positive	8	10,0	2	2.5	10	12.5	
Total		76	76	95.0	4	5.0	80	

Table 3 shows that of the 70 respondents who had negative actions, there were 68 respondents (85.0%) who experienced an unforeseen event and only 2 respondents (2.5%) did not experience an adverse event. Meanwhile, of the 10 respondents who had positive actions, there were 8 respondents (10.0%) who experienced an unlucky event and only 2 respondents (2.5%) who did not experience an unlucky pregnancy. The results of the statistical analysis test using Fisher's Exact Test obtained a value (p value = $0.074 > 0.05$), so H_a was rejected and H_o was accepted. This means that there is no relationship between adolescent actions and Unwanted Pregnancy among teenagers in the North Konawe Regency 2022. This is shown by 2 respondents who took negative actions but did not experience Unwanted Pregnancy.

The Relationship Between Permissive Parenting Patterns and Unwanted Pregnancies in Adolescents in the North Konawe Regency Area

Table 4. Relationship between permissive parenting and unwanted pregnancy

No	Permissive Parenting Patterns	Unwanted Pregnancy				Amount		P Value
		Yes		Not		n	%	
		n	%	n	%			
1	Yes	52	65,0	1	1,2	53	66,2	0,109
2	Not	24	30,0	3	3,8	27	33,8	
Total		76	95,0	4	5,0	80	100	

Table 4 shows that of the 53 respondents who had a permissive parenting style, there were 52 respondents (65.0%) who experienced Unwanted Pregnancy and only 3 respondents (3.8%) did not experience Unwanted Pregnancy. Meanwhile, of the 9 respondents who had positive actions, there were 8 respondents (10.0%) who experienced Unwanted Pregnancy and only 1 respondent (1.2%) did not experience Unwanted Pregnancy. The results of the statistical analysis test using Fisher's Exact Test obtained a value (p value = 0.109 > 0.05), so H_a was rejected and H_o was accepted. This illustrates that there is no relationship between permissive parenting and Unwanted Pregnancy among teenagers in the North Konawe Regency 2022. This is based on 1 respondent who had a permissive parenting pattern but experienced Unwanted Pregnancy.

The Relationship Between Peer Pressure and Unwanted Pregnancy in Adolescents in the North Konawe Regency Area.

Table 5. Relationship between peer pressure and unwanted pregnancy

No	Peer Pressure	Unwanted Pregnancy				Amount		P Value
		Yes		Not		n	%	
		n	%	n	%			
1	Negative	52	65,0	2	2,5	54	67,5	0,592
2	Positive	24	30,0	2	2,5	26	32,5	
Total		76	95,0	4	5,0	80	100	

Table 5 shows that of the 54 respondents who had negative peer pressure, there were 52 respondents (65.0%) who experienced Unwanted Pregnancy and only 2 respondents (2.5%) who did not experience Unwanted Pregnancy. Meanwhile, of the 9 respondents who had positive actions, there were 8 respondents (10.0%) who experienced Unwanted Pregnancy and only 2 respondents (2.5%) who did not experience Unwanted Pregnancy. The results of statistical analysis tests using Fisher's Exact Test obtained a value (p value = 0.109 > 0.05), then H_a is rejected and H_o is accepted. This illustrates that there is no relationship between peer pressure and Unwanted Pregnancy among teenagers in the North Konawe Regency 2022. From the results of data analysis obtained by teenagers with negative peer pressure, there were 2 respondents who did not experience Unwanted Pregnancy.

The Relationship Between Technology Use and Unwanted Pregnancy in Teenagers in the North Konawe Regency Area.

Table 6. Relationship between technology use and unwanted pregnancy

No	Use Technology	Unwanted Pregnancy				Amount		P Value
		Yes		Not		n	%	
		n	%	n	%			
1	Positive	61	76.2	1	1.3	62	77.5	0,034
2	Negative	15	18.8	3	3.7	18	22.5	
	Total	76	95.0	4	5.0	80	100	

Table 6 shows that of the 62 respondents who used technology positively, there were 61 respondents (76.2%) who experienced Unwanted Pregnancy and 1 respondent (1.3%) did not experience Unwanted Pregnancy. Meanwhile, of the 18 respondents who used technology negatively, 15 respondents (18.8%) experienced unwanted pregnancy and 3 respondents (3.7%) did not experience Unwanted Pregnancy. The results of the statistical analysis test using Fisher's Exact Test obtained a value (p value = 0.034 < α = 0.05), so H_a was accepted and H_o was rejected. This illustrates that there is a relationship between the use of technology and Unwanted Pregnancy among teenagers in the North Konawe Regency in 2022. This is illustrated by 61 teenagers who use positive technology but experience Unwanted Pregnancy.

The Relationship between Religiosity and Unwanted Pregnancy in Adolescents in the North Konawe Regency Area.

Table 7. Relationship between Religiosity and Unwanted Pregnancy

No	Religiusitas	Unwanted Pregnancy				Amount		P Value
		Yes		Not		n	%	
		n	%	n	%			
1	High	73	91.25	1	1.25	74	92.5	0,001
2	Lacking	3	3.75	3	3.75	6	7.5	
	Total	76	95.0	4	5.0	80	100	

Table 7 shows that of the 74 respondents who had less religiosity, 73 respondents (91.25%) experienced Unwanted Pregnancy and 1 respondent (1.25%) did not experience Unwanted Pregnancy. Meanwhile, of the 6 respondents who had high religiosity, there were 3 respondents (3.75%) who experienced Unwanted Pregnancy and 3 respondents (3.75%) who did not experience Unwanted Pregnancy. The results of the statistical analysis test using Fisher's Exact Test obtained a value (p value = 0.001 < α = 0.05), so H_a was accepted and H_o was rejected. This means that there is a relationship between religiosity and Unwanted Pregnancy among teenagers in the North Konawe Regency 2022. From these data it can be said that the majority of respondents with less religiosity experienced Unwanted Pregnancy.

DISCUSSION

Globally, a lot of research has been carried out to describe the risky sexual behavior of teenagers and its impact on Unwanted Pregnancy and is still increasing in the last 5 years. [25,38–41]. Similar research in Southeast Sulawesi is still small scale and few [24], Unwanted pregnancies among teenagers often occur in Indonesia. This is caused by various factors that trigger pregnancy in teenagers and these factors include lack of knowledge, attitudes and actions regarding promiscuity, peer pressure, parenting patterns,

access to pornography, use of technology, religiosity, and many others. The results of this study show that the factors causing unwanted pregnancies in teenagers are lack of knowledge and attitudes of teenagers, easy access to social media, permissive attitudes of teenagers, and parenting patterns of parents.

The aim of this research is to analyze the determinants of Unwanted Pregnancy and find the dominant variables that have an impact on Unwanted Pregnancy cases. So it is hoped that this research can contribute to reducing pregnancy rates among teenagers in Southeast Sulawesi in particular and Indonesia in general. The intended determinants of Unwanted Pregnancy are the variables of knowledge, attitudes, actions, permissive parenting patterns, peer pressure, use of technology and religiosity among teenagers in the North Konawe Regency area.

Knowledge is one of the predictors of Unwanted Pregnancy in adolescents. This research shows that there is no relationship between adolescent knowledge and Unwanted Pregnancy. Most respondents have knowledge about contraception, especially the use of condoms which according to them can prevent them from Unwanted Pregnancy. However, they have low knowledge about conception, even though conception is a phase of life that really determines the quality of human resources. Even though they receive information about menarche, the fertile period, HIV and AIDS through socialization at school or in their living environment, they do not fully understand conception. On the other hand, they have awareness about Unwanted Pregnancy as a result of risky sexual behavior, but this is not followed by good consideration. Thus, their knowledge does not become a reference for avoiding risky sexual behavior, even ending in Unwanted Pregnancy.

This research is in line with research by Mai et al (2019), knowledge about reproductive health and HIV prevention did not show a statistically significant relationship with premarital sexual behavior among adolescents in Cambodia.

This research is in line with research by Pakpahan et al (2021) which states that the majority of teenagers have an understanding of risky sexual behavior and are aware of the consequences of unsafe sex, however, they still behave deviantly which leads to Unwanted Pregnancy. However, Ayele's (2018) research showed that 52.9% of respondents who experienced Unwanted Pregnancy had poor knowledge about the occurrence of conception. Fitriani's research (2019) has also identified that teenagers who have low knowledge of sexuality have a greater chance of deviant behavior, when compared to teenagers who have good knowledge [25]. The results of these two studies are different from the analysis of this study which claims that both teenagers who have poor knowledge and those who have good knowledge both have the same chance of experiencing Unwanted Pregnancy.

At the same time, deviant sexual behavior is largely determined by the negative attitudes that teenagers have. This research found that there was a relationship between attitudes and Unwanted Pregnancy which was not entirely a reflection of their knowledge about sexual behavior and Unwanted Pregnancy, but rather attitudes that considered virginity was not important as a determinant of Unwanted Pregnancy. Teenagers admit to having sexual relations with the right people voluntarily and without coercion from anyone. Most teenagers engage in risky sexual acts in dating, including holding hands, hugging, kissing cheeks and foreheads, kissing, necking, touching sensitive organs (touching breasts and genitals). Teenage boys admit to using condoms as protection which are sold among teenagers themselves. They also stated that dating is a very important thing to go through as a stage of getting to know each other and consider it important to fulfill all their partner's requests. Adolescents who behave sexually at risk see this as normal when dating, because it is considered proof of their love for their partner.

Thus, these reasons illustrate that teenagers consider sex before marriage to be normal, and there are even teenagers who are proud to talk about their risky behavior and end up with Unwanted Pregnancy. This argument is in line with Jannah and Cahyono's research[32] which identifies adolescent attitudes that are very influential in responding to sexual behavioral stimuli that can result in Unwanted Pregnancy. This research was also supported by [42] which shows that dating status has a significant relationship with deviant sexual behavior.

However, this study claims there is no relationship between teenage actions and Unwanted Pregnancy. Some teenagers whose actions were positive actually experienced Unwanted Pregnancy and some of those who experienced Unwanted Pregnancy were the result of coercion in the form of rape. Coercion does not only come from peers, but also comes from family, for example stepfathers, uncles and even siblings. This phenomenon colored brutal sexual acts, so that the young women who were victims of sexual violence chose to end Unwanted Pregnancy with abortion. Sadly, society's treatment of Unwanted Pregnancy and abortion cases is considered normal, they are no longer seen as serious problems, and they are even silent even though they know and understand that this

happens. Pretending that nothing had happened, they held a traditional party and a large reception for the families of teenage couples who were pregnant out of wedlock.

The description of the phenomenon above shows a change in people's behavior with the meaning of 'taboo' which used to be glorified, but now the value has shifted. The 'culture of shame' has gone far from civilized society which upholds self-esteem and 'family stigma' is no longer a scourge, and local people see cases of Unwanted Pregnancy no longer as a 'family disgrace'. These changes are evidenced by various reasons other than those mentioned previously. The reasons referred to include; some cases of early marriage that were found had the same history as their parents, so it was considered normal; loose parenting system and non-formal education at home, with almost non-existent parenting skills. The Reproductive Health and Sexuality Education Program in schools is only limited to counseling, not integrated into the existing curriculum and adolescent reproductive health services are less effective because it is strange if teenagers come to reproductive health services which most people understand that these services are only for women. already married.

This research shows that there is no relationship between permissive parenting styles and Unwanted Pregnancy in adolescents. A permissive parenting style tends to prioritize children's comfort, so that they act like friends and rarely have strict rules, as a result parents become weak in responding to their children's every wish. They freely do what they want, including the freedom to date and misuse their time and misplace the trust given by their parents when they leave the house. Ultimately it leads to risky behavior. However, most parents admit that they strictly forbid their children from dating.

The results of this analysis are in line with Widman's research [43] found that the role of parents is not significant in terms of decision making and open communication, especially those related to adolescent sexual behaviour. Communication regarding reproduction and sexuality is very minimal, and some parents still consider this information not suitable for discussing openly with their teenagers. These two reasons cause teenagers to grow up in an environment that does not care about the importance of understanding reproductive health and sexuality. The description of this case actually makes teenagers more curious about their sexual behaviour, so they look for other sources that are not necessarily sources of accurate, safe and reliable information. Finally they were trapped and ended up with an Unwanted Pregnancy case.

It can be concluded that with permissive parenting, children should be given better direction with a friend-like approach, but if parenting skills are lacking, this does not happen. This study identifies daily situations and conditions regarding the phenomenon of Unwanted Pregnancy which are increasingly surprising and there is an inconsistency in this study, namely that parents feel embarrassed to communicate with their children about the concept of sexuality and reproduction, even though they know that there are many cases of Unwanted Pregnancy and abortion. This finding also correlates with the parents' background, most of whom experienced early marriage, so that two-way communication skills between parents and teenage children are almost absent. There is no discussion about Reproductive Health and Sexuality in the family which is articulated in permissive parenting, so the findings of this study conclude that good teenagers with permissive parenting do not experience Unwanted Pregnancy and conversely teenagers with non-permissive parenting are likely to experience Unwanted Pregnancy.

The role of parents is important to pay attention to because teenagers have the potential to behave sexually freely. Freedom to do the things you want occurs due to several factors, including; parents do not set limits on when to be at home. Punishment does not exist as a deterrent if children make mistakes, including if they experience Unwanted Pregnancy and break the rules. There is a correlation between no communication and limited home hours, parents not knowing their children's friends and not knowing their children's activities. Parents give their children freedom to do whatever they want, for example the freedom to date, but there is no explanation as to what the impact of dating is.

Several studies have identified the phenomenon of Unwanted Pregnancy as contributing to the rise of early marriages which result in the death of the mother giving birth or the death of the newborn. [10,44]. This study also found that early marriage or married status after experiencing Unwanted Pregnancy was quite high and this was partly due to experiencing Unwanted Pregnancy through coercion and harassment. This is caused by; adolescent behavior that dares to be different, free travel, curiosity about the body and sexuality, ignorance about the impact of risky sexual behavior. This is made worse by the lack of appropriate and accurate information regarding reproduction and sexuality that they receive from both formal and non-formal education, so they do not have

accurate understanding and communication and negotiation skills. On the other hand, they do not receive support from their parents because most parents have a low level of education and also a history of early marriage. Thus, the correlation between permissive parenting styles and teenagers born from early marriages are twice as likely to experience Unwanted Pregnancy.

Adolescents have a tendency to interact with each other, socialize and provide encouragement and motivation to other peers emotionally. So the presence of peers can have a big influence on their development. Teenagers admit that they date because of invitations from their peers and also feel like they are behind the times if they don't follow their friends' invitations, so they are influenced by risky sexual behavior which leads to early marriage. This research found that there was no relationship between the role of peers and Unwanted Pregnancy in adolescents. Most teenagers stated that friendship was important and dating was normal and very important in their relationships. However, it was found that teenagers with negative peer pressure did not experience Unwanted Pregnancy, on the contrary, teenagers with positive peer pressure experienced Unwanted Pregnancy.

Research by Alzate et al (2018), Jannah (2018), dan Damtie et al (2022) which states that premarital sexual behavior is very significantly related to peer pressure because teenagers usually tend to follow the behavior practiced by their close friends. One of the triggers for high levels of adolescent sexual behavior is access to pornography. Teenagers usually use technology such as smartphones and the like to access information they want to know, including sexual and pornographic content. This research shows that there is a relationship between technology use and unwanted pregnancy in adolescents. Teenagers who are accustomed to using technology are ultimately influenced by deviant behavior which leads to Unwanted Pregnancy. Teenagers admit that they spend more time on their cellphones than interacting with other people. From mobile phones they get new experiences by getting to know new people.

The applications on their cellphones make them spend a lot of time, such as WhatsApp, this application is used to chat online, send files to each other, exchange photos and videos, and use it to carry out videocall activities. Several respondents admitted that they have a chat group in WA which consists of their friends, in this group sometimes chats occur or "naughty" pictures are exchanged. Most teenagers stated that they occasionally watched pornographic images/videos together with their friends or with their boyfriends.

On research [46,47] which states that pornography can influence the behavior of teenagers, inspiring them to engage in risky sexual behavior and for vulnerable teenagers it can become a psychological addiction that leads to sexual disorders. Pornography has devastating consequences. A person who practices his religion well will tend to behave in accordance with good norms and religion shapes morals and beliefs within the individual. This research shows that there is a relationship between religiosity and unwanted pregnancy among teenagers in the North Konawe Regency area. This is based on the fact that most teenagers' religiosity is in the deficient category, which causes Unwanted Pregnancy. Obedience in performing worship and reading the holy books is considered to be very lacking, with people procrastinating and even not doing it. Religiosity is also largely determined by family and environmental factors. The lack of guidance from parents regarding understanding obligatory worship creates the perception that parents seem to ignore them. Worshiping with family is admitted to be rare or even never. Several respondents also had a history of mothers who also experienced a history of Unwanted Pregnancy at a young age.

According to Afandi (2018) and Sari & Indriani (2021), adolescent religiosity is related to Unwanted Pregnancy, where adolescents with low religiosity and self-control have a risk of engaging in risky sexual behavior which has an impact on Unwanted Pregnancy.

Based on the phenomenon and description of risky adolescent behavior, lack of understanding, promiscuity as a contributor to cases of unwanted pregnancy. This is also caused by excessive dating activity, which causes teenagers to have casual sex and end up with Unwanted Pregnancy. On the other hand, teenagers feel more comfortable expressing opinions and telling about teenage life to their peers compared to their parents. So it is necessary to empower a forum that embraces all parties to build closeness between parents and teenagers. Culturally, a traditional meeting is a meeting that can bring together community members, parents, teenagers and all residents of a particular area in the context of religious and traditional holidays. This requires support and support from the local government, in order to empower traditional groups as a forum for open communication between residents.

CONCLUSION

This research shows that negative attitudes, use of technology and religiosity are the dominant factors that have a significant influence on Unwanted Pregnancy among teenagers in North Konawe Regency.

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